

EFFECT OF ALCOHOL TREATMENT ON UTILIZATION OF PROTEIN FROM SOYBEAN MEAL BY COCKERELS

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ABSTRACT

Two cockerels bioassays were performed to evaluate utilization of alcohol treated soybean meal (SBM). In the study, 30 and 50% (v/v) propanol, 30% (v/v) isopropanol and 50% (v/v) ethanol treatments did not improve utilization of SBM. The protein efficiency ratio of the cockerels did not differ from the control. Concluding that alcohol did not improve the performance or feed efficiency rate in the chicks.

Key words: Alcohol, Soybean, cockerel, ruminal degradation, performance.

INTRODUCTION

Physical or chemical treatments of protein to reduce protein degradation in the rumen can increase gains under certain feeding situations. Improved nitrogen utilization and performance in growing lambs (Faichneq, 1971; Barg, 1972) and improved feed efficiency in steers (Spears *et al*; 1980) have been reported with formaldehyde (HcHo) treatment of soybean meal (SBM). Nitrogen (N) must be adequate for microbial growth in the rumen to maintain fiber digestion and protein flow to the small intestine under ideal conditions, high quality protein would escape ruminal digestion, but be digested postruminally.

The proportion of dietary protein ingested by ruminants and available for postruminal digestion and absorption depends on rate and extent of ruminal protein digestion (Orskov and McDonald, 1979).

Van der Aar *et al* (1982) observed that treatment of soybean meal (SBM) with various alcohol-water solutions reduced not only solubility of SBM protein in Burroughs mineral mixture, but also rate of digestion in situ. Furthermore, it was shown that SBM protein soluble after treatment released less ammonia during in vitro digestion than soluble protein from untreated SBM. These observations indicate that alcohol treatment released less ammonia during in vitro digestion than soluble protein from untreated SBM. These observations indicate that alcohol treatment may have a positive effect on utilization of SBM protein by ruminants.

The objective of this study was to determine the effect of alcohol treatment of SBM on protein available to cockerels

EXPERIMENTS DESIGN

Feed and water were provided ad libitum. The cockerels were weighed initially (8 d.old) and on d 7 and 14 of the study on those days, feed consumption was also determined. Feed refusals were collected on d 14 and analyzed for N content.

One hundred twenty growing cockerels were allotted randomly to eight treatments, with each treatment being replicated three times. Soybean meal (untreated) or SBM treated with 100% (v/v) water, 30 and 50% (v/v) isopropanol, 30 and 50% (v/v) propanol or 30% and 50% (v/v) ethanol were evaluated. Each diet was formulated to contain 23% of the crude protein (CP) requirement according to the NRC (1979) food composition as shown in table 1.

TABLE 1: Composition (% dry matter) of Basal diets fed to cockerels

Ingredients	%
Corn meal	85.26
Corngluten meal	3.27
Alfalfa meal	1.63
Corn oil	3.27
Dicalcium phosphate	3.60
Limestone	1.63
NaCl	.82
MnSO ₄	.08
Chloride	.16
ZnCO ₃	.03
Chlortetracycline	.08
Vit. Mix	.16

Hexane extracted, dehulled soybean was soaked in various alcohol water solutions for 30 min at 22°C. A Solvent to SBM ratio of 2:5:1 was used. After soaking, SBM was squeezed through eight layers of cheese cloth and dried by forced air at room temperature.

All experiments were analyzed statistically by analysis of variance. If significant differences were noted in the analysis of variance, multiple comparison between treatments were made by the LSD method (Carmer and Swanson, 1973)

TABLE 2: Effect of alcohol treatment on cockerel performance and protein efficiency ratio (PER)^a

Response criteria: Treatment	Feed intake g/d	Weight gain g/d	Gain/Feed	PER
Control	15.8	4.8	.30 ^b	2.8 ^{bc}
100% Water	16.3	5.6	.34 ^d	2.9 ^{bc}
30% Ethanol	16.8	5.4	.32 ^{bcd}	2.9 ^{bc}
50% Ethanol	16.7	5.7	.34 ^{cd}	2.9 ^{bc+}
30% Propanol	16.5	5.1	.31 ^{bc}	2.7 ^{bc}
50% Propanol	16.5	5.1	.31 ^{bc}	2.6 ^b
30% Isopropanol	18.1	5.6	.31 ^{bc}	2.7 ^{bc}
50% Isopropanol	16.1	4.8	.30 ^b	2.7 ^{bc}
\bar{X}	16.6	5.3	.32	2.8
SE^e	.96	.43	.014	.15

^a means of triplicate of five chicks during the period 8 to 22 d of post hatching.

^b No significant difference observed

^{c,d} means in the same column followed by different superscripts differ (P<.05)

^eSE Standard error of the mean.

\bar{X} means

RESULTS

Because alcohol treatment of soybean meal did not affect performance of cockerels fed a corn-SBM diet, results of this experiment are not present in tabular form. Intake, grain and feed efficiency

(gain/feed) were similar for all treatments during both the first and second weeks of the intakes, growth rates and feed efficiencies were 29.1 g/d, 25.9 g/d and .89, respectively. During the second week, feed intakes, growth rates and feed efficiencies were 49.6 g/d, 36.8 g/d and 74, respectively.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Cockerels fed a corn-soybean meal diet containing 23% cp had equivalent performance to those receiving diets in which untreated soybean meal was replaced by alcohol-treated soybean meal. Differences in performance of cockerels feed a semipurified diet containing 10% cp (table 2) could be completely attributed to selection by the animals for N in the diet protein efficiency ratio for all SBM treatments was equal to that for the untreated SBM (table 2). These results indicate that alcohol treatment of SBM did not result in decreased bioavailability of protein is a very important characteristic of this process because other methods of decreasing rumen degradability of SBM protein have been reported to reduced protein bioavailability. Spears *et al* (1980) showed that excessive treatment of SBM with formaldehyde depressed chick performance. Similar depressions have been observed with excessive roasting of SBM (Plegge *et al*, 1982).

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